

C-Alkyl Resorcinols. Part II. Synthesis of Polyalkyl Resorcinols.

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Although monoalkyl resorcinols and their derivatives have been much studied, comparatively little work appears to have been done on polyalkyl resorcinols. 4:6-Dialkyl resorcinols were synthesised for study of their phenol coefficients by Klarmann (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, **48**, 2358). The present work was undertaken with the object of synthesising typical polyalkyl resorcinols containing more than two alkyl groups, which might be valuable as antiseptics.

After this work was far advanced, Rosenmund, Buchwald and Deligiannis (*Arch. Pharm.*, 1933, **271**, 342) reported the synthesis of a number of 2:4:6-trialkylresorcinols, which were obtained by reduction of 4-alkyl-2:6-diacylresorcinols, produced from diacyl esters of 4-*n*-alkylresorcinols by the action of aluminium chloride in nitrobenzene solution.

In the present work, 4:6-diethyl-2-methyl-, 4-ethyl-5:6-dimethyl-, 4:6-diethyl-5-methyl-, and 4:6-diethyl-5:6-dimethyl-resorcinols have been synthesised, through the intermediate ketones and aldehydes. The C-alkyl resorcinol ketones obtained are of interest on account of their possible value as anthelmintics (*cf.* Karrer and Rosenfeld, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1921, **4**, 707). The *ortho*-hydroxy structure of the intermediate resorcylaldehydes was confirmed by (i) condensation with 5:6-dimethoxy-1-hydrindone by Perkin-Robinson method (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, **91**, 1073), when characteristic pyrylium chlorides were obtained and (ii) by condensation with malonic or acetoacetic esters in the presence of piperidine by the Knoevenagel method (*Ber.*, 1904, **37**, 4461) which gave 3-carbethoxy- or 3-acetylalkyl coumarins.

The various polyalkyl resorcinols are in general unstable crystalline substances and gradually decompose on standing. They give a bluish colouration with aqueous ferric chloride which rapidly fades away, probably due to oxidation. They are characterised by their high melting *p*-nitrobenzoyl derivatives, and further, those with their *o*-positions to the hydroxyl group free, were converted into alkyl coumarins by Pechmann condensation with acetoacetic ester and malic acid.

Synthesis of 4 : 6-Diethyl-2-methylresorcinol.

4 : 6-Diethylresorcinol was prepared according to Weiss and Kratz (*Monatsch.*, 1929, **51**, 386) and various reactions studied (*cf.* Part I, *Bombay University Journal*, 1935, p. 209). Although it did not undergo the Höesch reaction with acetonitrile, it was readily converted by the Gattermann reaction into 2 : 6-dihydroxy-3 : 5-diethylbenzaldehyde (I), a γ -resorcylic aldehyde. The bright yellow colour of the aldehyde may be explained by its existence in the tautomeric quinonoid form (*cf.* Robertson and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 2196). Reduction of the aldehyde (I) by zinc amalgam prepared by the improved method of Robinson and Shah (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1491) gave the required 4 : 6-diethyl-2-methylresorcinol (II).

Synthesis of 4-Ethyl-5 : 6-dimethylresorcinol.

4-Ethyl-5-methylresorcinol (Robinson and Shah, *loc. cit.*), the reduction product of oracetophenone, gave by the Gattermann reaction the aldehyde, whose probable constitution is that of a β -resorcylic aldehyde viz., 6-methyl-5-ethyl-2 : 4-dihydroxybenzaldehyde (III), and not that of γ -resorcylic aldehyde viz., 2 : 6-dihydroxy-4-methyl-5-ethyl-benzaldehyde. The β -resorcylic aldehyde structure is supported by (i) analogy with known cases of Gattermann reaction on resorcinol derivatives, in which the aldehyde group usually enters the β -position which is much more accessible; and (ii) by the properties of the 3-carbethoxycoumarin resulting from the Knoevenagel condensation of the aldehyde with malonic ester, the coumarin derivative in solution in concentrated sulphuric acid or in dilute alkali showing strong fluorescence, characteristic of a 7-hydroxycoumarin, which can only result from a β -resorcylic aldehyde (*cf.* Collie and Chrystall, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 1804; Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, **8**, 407; Dey, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, **107**, 1614, 1621). The aldehyde gave with 5 : 6-dimethoxy-1-hydrindone the characteristic pyrylium chloride. The Knoevenagel condensation with acetoacetic ester, however, produced abnormally a crystalline pyrylium salt with a green metallic reflex, instead of the expected 3-acetylcoumarin derivative. The

pyrylium salt dissolved in alcohol with a permanganate colour, which turned deep blue on adding alkali. The formation of the pyrylium salt must be due to the further condensation of the 3-acetylcoumarin derivative, initially formed, with a second molecule of the hydroxy aldehyde to give the chalkone, which with hydrochloric acid would form the pyrylium salt. An analogous compound has only recently been obtained by Le Fèvre (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 450) from salicylaldehyde and acetoacetic ester in ethereal perchloric acid with hydrogen chloride as condensing agent. This interesting reaction will be more closely studied. Reduction of the aldehyde in the usual way led to the phenol of probable constitution, 4-ethyl-5 : 6-dimethyl resorcinol (IV).

Synthesis of 4:6-Diethyl-5-methylresorcinol.

4-Ethyl-5-methylresorcinol by the Höesch reaction afforded the ketone whose probable constitution is 5-ethyl-6-methyl-2:4-dihydroxyacetophenone (VI). The ketone has been assigned the constitution (VI) of a β -acetylresorcinol derivative on the following grounds:— (i) Analogy with other cases of Höesch reaction on resorcinol compounds, (ii) the acetyl group cannot be introduced in the γ -position in the resorcinol nucleus by the Höesch reaction, as shown by the observation that 4:6-diethylresorcinol does not undergo the Höesch reaction, (iii) the diethylmethylresorcinol (VII) produced by the Clemmensen reduction of the ketone, when condensed with acetoacetic ester and malic acid give coumarins, which do not show fluorescence and are, therefore, 5-hydroxycoumarins, which can only result from a β -acetylresorcinol compound. If

the ketone was a γ -acetylresorcinol derivative, the coumarins obtained would be 7-hydroxycoumarins.

Clemmensen reduction of the ketone yielded the phenol of the probable constitution 4:6-diethyl-5-methylresorcinol (VII).

Synthesis of 4:6-Diethyl-2:5-dimethylresorcinol.

3:5-Diethyl-4-methyl-2:6-dihydroxybenzaldehyde (VIII) was obtained from 4:6-diethyl-5-methylresorcinol (VII) in the usual manner. Its deep yellow colour may be explained similarly to (I). Reduction in aqueous alcoholic solution under properly regulated condition gave an excellent yield of 4:6-diethyl-2:5-dimethylresorcinol, the first tetra-alkylresorcinol (IX) to be synthesised.

The facile reduction by the Clemmensen method of 3:5-diethyl-2:6-dihydroxybenzaldehyde is remarkable, in view of the fact that 2:4-diacetyl- and 2:4-dipropionylresorcinols yield by Clemmensen reduction 4-ethyl- and 4-propylresorcinols, the acetyl-group in position 2 being split off (Rosenmund *et al*, *loc. cit.*).

EXPERIMENTAL.

3:5-Diethyl-2:6-dihydroxybenzaldehyde (I) was prepared by the Adams and Levene's modification of the Gattermann reaction (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, **45**, 2373). To 4:6-diethylresorcinol (7 g.) dissolved in dry ether (150 c.c.) zinc cyanide (9.3 g.) was added, the mechanical stirrer started and dry hydrogen chloride gas passed in rapidly. After 1 hour, the ketimide hydrochloride began to separate as an oil, after which hydrogen chloride was passed for another hour. Ether was decanted off and the oily residue was washed with dry ether. Water (100 c.c.) was then added and the mixture heated at 100° for 1 hour. The oil which separated on cooling was extracted

with ether. The residue from the ether extract which distilled as a yellow oil at 142-144°/2 mm. gradually solidified on cooling giving deep yellow flat needles, m.p. 68-70°. (Found: C, 68.0; H, 7.3. $C_{11}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 68.1; H, 7.2 per cent). It decomposes gradually on standing, the solid becoming pasty and ultimately oily after few days. It gave a deep violet colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. The *p*-nitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from dilute acetic acid in long chocolate coloured needles melting at 217-19°. (Found: N, 12.7. $C_{17}H_{18}O_4N_3$ requires N, 12.8 per cent).

Ethyl 6:8-diethyl-5-hydroxycoumarin-3-carboxylate.—Ethyl malonate (0.8 g.) was added to the aldehyde (I, 1 g.), 5 drops of piperidine were added at 0° and the reaction mixture was left for 2 days at room temperature. The dark yellow paste on treatment with dilute hydrochloric acid gave yellowish needles which crystallised from benzene in yellow needles, m.p. 155-57°. (Found**: C, 66.1; H, 6.3. $C_{16}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 66.2; H, 6.2 per cent). It did not show fluorescence in concentrated sulphuric acid solution or in alkaline solution.

6:8-Diethyl-5-hydroxy-5':6'-dimethoxy-2:3(3':2')-indenobenzopyrylium Chloride.—Dry hydrogen chloride gas was passed for 2 hours into a solution of the aldehyde (I, 1g.) and 5:6-dimethoxy-1-hydrindone (1 g.) in dry ethyl acetate (5 c.c.). The deep orange leaflets obtained were washed several times with dry ether and dried, m.p. 209-10°. (Found: Cl, 9.4. $C_{22}H_{23}O_4Cl$ requires Cl, 9.2 per cent). The salt is easily hydrolysed, as the deep red aqueous acidic solution gradually decolourised and a yellowish precipitate, probably the related chalkone, ultimately separated. The perchlorate separated in deep red tiny needles on the addition of perchloric acid (5 c.c.). It was filtered, washed with dry methyl alcohol and dried, m.p. 155-58°. (Found: Cl, 7.9. $C_{22}H_{23}O_8Cl$ requires Cl, 7.9 per cent).

4:6-Diethyl-2-methylresorcinol (I).—To 30 g. of zinc amalgam, prepared from zinc dust according to Robiusion and Shah (*loc. cit.*), the aldehyde (I, 7 g.) was added, followed by 50 c.c. of dilute hydrochloric acid (1:2) and the mixture heated at 100°. After 1 hour, 10 c.c. of concentrated HCl were added and the heating was continued for another hour. The solution was decanted off, saturated with common salt and extracted with ether. The unreacted zinc amalgam was also extracted with ether. The residue from the combined ether extract distilled as a colourless viscous oil at 170°/12 mm., and solidified on cooling in colourless plates, yield 4 g., m.p. 51-53°.

(Found : C, 73'0; H, 8'5. $C_{11}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 73'3; H, 8'9 per cent). It gave a transient blue colouration with aqueous ferric chloride.

The *di-p-nitrobenzoyl* derivative separated in long needles on shaking together an ethereal solution of *p*-nitrobenzoyl chloride and sodium hydroxide solution of (II). It crystallised from acetone-ethyl alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 161-62°. (Found : N, 6'2. $C_{25}H_{22}O_8N_2$ requires N, 5'9 per cent).

Dibenzoyl derivative of Orsacetophenone.—A mixture of orsacetophenone (2 g.), benzoyl chloride (5 c.c.) and pyridine (12 c.c.) was left at room temperature for 12 hours, acidified with dilute sulphuric acid and extracted with ether. The oily residue from the ethereal extract solidified after several days and crystallised from dilute alcohol in greyish shining plates, m.p. 97-98°, yield 0.6g. (Found : C, 73.4; H, 4.7. $C_{23}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 73.8; H, 4.8 per cent).

Di-p-nitrobenzoyl Derivative of 4-Ethyl-5-methylresorcinol crystallised from acetone-ethyl alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 173°-174°. (Found: N, 6.5. $C_{23}H_{18}O_8N_2$ requires N, 6.2 per cent). It is insoluble in the usual organic solvents except acetone.

4-Ethyl-5-methyl-6-acetoxy-mercuri-resorcinol.—4-Ethyl-5-methylresorcinol (1 g.) in alcoholic solution was added to a suspension of mercuric acetate (2 g.) in the same solvent. The yellow product crystallised from boiling acetic acid in tiny orange needles which blackened at 200° and did not melt up to 315°, yield 2.1 g. (Found: Hg, 48.5. $C_{11}H_{14}O_4$ Hg requires Hg, 48.9 per cent).

5-Methyl-6-ethyl-7-hydroxycoumarin.—Concentrated sulphuric acid (85%; 15 c.c.) was slowly added to a mixture of 4-ethyl-5-methylresorcinol (1.5 g.) and malic acid (1.3 g.), and after 12 hours was heated at 100° for 1 hour, cooled and poured into ice-cold water. The precipitate crystallised from dilute alcohol in greyish needles, m.p. 211-12°, yield 1 g. (Found*: C, 70.4; H, 5.6. $C_{12}H_{13}O_3$ requires C, 70.6; H, 5.9 per cent). It gave a light blue fluorescence in concentrated sulphuric acid and in alkaline solution and hence it is formulated as a 7-hydroxy coumarin. (*cf.* Collie and Chrystall, *loc. cit.*; Chakravarti, *loc. cit.*; Dey, *loc. cit.*)

4:7-Dimethyl-6-ethyl-5-hydroxycoumarin.—A mixture of concentrated sulphuric acid (85%; 10 c.c.), 4-ethyl-5-methylresorcinol (1.5 g.) and ethyl acetoacetate (1.3 g.) was kept at room temperature for 1 hour, heated at 100°, cooled and poured into ice-cold water. The dirty pasty mass solidified after 2 hours and crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless flat needles,

m.p. 187-89°, yield 1.3 g. (Found*: C, 71.3; H, 6.5. $C_{13}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 71.6; H, 6.4 per cent). It is regarded as a 5-hydroxy compound as it does not show light blue fluorescence in sulphuric acid and in alkaline solution.

2-Methyl-3-ethyl-4:6-dihydroxybenzaldehyde (III) was prepared similarly to (I) from 4-ethyl-5-methylresorcinol (8.5 g.) dissolved in dry ether (120 c.c.) and zinc cyanide (14 g.). Hydrogen chloride gas was passed for 2½ hours, after which the separated oily ketimide hydrochloride was heated with water (200 c.c.) at 100° for 1½ hours. The solid, which separated on cooling, crystallised from dilute ethyl alcohol in yellow needles, m.p. 161-62°, yield 5.1 g. (Found:* C, 66.8; H, 6.8. $C_{10}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 66.6; H, 6.7 per cent). It gave a dark violet colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. The *p-nitrophenylhydrazone* crystallised from dilute alcohol in orange wooly needles, m.p. 255°-257°. (Found: N, 13.1. $C_{16}H_{17}O_4N_3$ requires N, 13.3 per cent).

Ethyl 5-methyl-6-ethyl-7-hydroxycoumarin-3-carboxylate was prepared from the foregoing aldehyde (III, 1 g.), malonic ester (0.9 g.) and 4 drops of piperidine. It crystallised from benzene in yellowish thick plates, m.p. 165-67°, yield 1 g. (Found: C, 65.2; H, 6.2. $C_{15}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 65.2; H, 5.8 per cent). It dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid giving a beautiful green fluorescence. Its alkaline solution also showed similar fluorescence.

Condensation of 2-Methyl-3-ethyl-4:6-dihydroxybenzaldehyde with ethyl acetoacetate.—To a mixture of the aldehyde (III, 1 g.) and ethyl acetoacetate (0.9 g.) piperidine (4 drops) was added at 0° and the mixture kept at room temperature for 5 hours. The pasty mass on treatment with dilute hydrochloric acid gave a dark red solid which crystallised from a mixture of acetic acid and dilute hydrochloric acid in brilliant needle-shaped crystals with a green metallic reflex, m.p. 295-98°. (Found: Cl, 8.1. $C_{24}H_{25}O_5Cl$ requires Cl, 8.3 per cent). The pyrylium salt (V) when dissolved in ethyl alcohol gave a permanganate colour, which changed to deep blue on addition of alkali, the blue colour base being formed. It gave a bluish green fluorescence with concentrated sulphuric acid.

5-Methyl-6-ethyl-7-hydroxy-5':6'-dimethoxy-2:3 (3':2')-indenobenzopyrylium Chloride.—Dry hydrochloric acid gas was passed at 0° for 2 hours into a mixture of the aldehyde (III, 1 g.) and 5:6-dimethoxy-1-hydrindone (1 g.) dissolved in the minimum quantity of ethyl acetate. The shining red plates darkened above 300°. (Found: Cl, 9.5. $C_{21}H_{21}O_4Cl$ requires Cl, 9.5 per cent). An aqueous acidic solution gradually decolourised and a yellowish precipitate ultimately

separated out. The *perchlorate* prepared by adding perchloric acid to a methyl alcoholic solution of the pyrylium chloride separated in orange needles. It darkened at 260° and did not melt up to 315° . (Found: Cl, 8.2 $C_{21}H_{21}O_8Cl$ requires Cl, 8.1 per cent).

4-Ethyl-5,6-dimethylresorcinol (IV).—A mixture of zinc amalgam (from 10 g. of zinc dust), the aldehyde (III, 2.3 g.) and 30 c.c. of dilute hydrochloric acid (1:1) was heated at 100° for 1 hour, when the feebly acidic solution gave no colouration with ferric chloride. The decanted solution deposited colourless crystals, which crystallised from hot alcohol in colourless flat needles, m.p. $145-46^{\circ}$, yield 1.4 g. (Found*: C, 72.4; H, 8.3. $C_{10}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 72.3; H, 8.4 per cent). It gave a greenish blue colouration with aqueous alcoholic ferric chloride. The phenol turned brown on keeping for a month and the melting point was then $120-130^{\circ}$. The *di-p-nitrobenzoyl* derivative crystallised from acetone-ethyl alcohol in tiny colourless needles, m.p. $224-25^{\circ}$. (Found: N, 6.0. $C_{24}H_{20}O_8N_2$ requires N, 6.0 per cent).

5-Ethyl-6-methyl-2:4-dihydroxyacetophenone (VI).—Dry hydrogen chloride gas was passed at 0° for 3 hours into a mixture of 4-ethyl-5-methylresorcinol (20 g.), acetonitrile (14 g.), dry ether (130 c.c.) and powdered fused zinc chloride (9.2 g.). The dark red oil which separated, solidified on keeping for 12 hours at 0° . It was washed with dry ether and treated with crushed ice. The yellowish crystalline substance was crystallised from boiling acetic acid in yellow plates, m.p. $237-38^{\circ}$, yield 11 g. (Found: Cl, 15.2. $C_{11}H_{16}O_2NCl$ requires Cl, 15.5 per cent). The hydrolysis of the ketimide hydrochloride was effected by boiling with water for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours. On cooling dirty brown small plates separated which were collected and crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether in brownish shining plates, m.p. $107-108^{\circ}$, yield 9 g. (Found*: C, 68.2; H, 7.4. $C_{11}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 68.1; H, 7.2 per cent). It gave a dark violet colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. The *dibenzoyl* derivative, which was prepared similarly to that of orsacetophenone, crystallised from dilute alcohol in shining flat needles, m.p. $61-63^{\circ}$, yield 0.26 g. (Found: C, 74.2; H, 5.6. $C_{25}C_{22}O_5$ requires C, 74.4; H, 5.5 per cent). It is insoluble in alkali and does not give any colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. The *phenylhydrazone* crystallised from dilute alcohol in yellow needles, m.p. $197-98^{\circ}$. (Found: N, 9.6. $C_{17}H_{21}O_2N_2$ requires N, 9.8 per cent).

4 : 6-Diethyl-5-methylresorcinol (VII).—A mixture of zinc amalgam (from 80 g. zinc dust), the foregoing ketone (VI, 20 g.) and dilute hydrochloric acid (1:1, 70 c.c.) was heated at 100° . When the

reaction moderated down, more dilute hydrochloric acid (60 c.c.) was added. Reduction required 2 hours. The product separating on cooling crystallised from hot water in flat colourless needles, m.p. 80° , yield 12 g. (Found*: C, 73.4; H, 9.0. $C_{11}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 73.3; H, 9.0 per cent). It gave a transient blue colouration with aqueous ferric chloride. The *di-p-nitrobenzoyl* derivative crystallised from boiling acetic acid in colourless shining needles, m.p. $243-45^{\circ}$. (Found : N, 6.0. $C_{25}H_{22}O_8N_2$ requires N, 5.9 per cent).

Diacetyl Derivative.—A mixture of the phenol (VIII, 2.3 g.), acetic anhydride (10 c.c.) and pyridine (5 drops) was kept for $1/2$ hour, refluxed for 1 hour and poured into water. It was crystallised from dilute alcohol in shining buttons, m.p. $69-70^{\circ}$, yield 1.7 g. (Found*: C, 68.1; H, 7.2. $C_{15}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 68.2; H, 7.6 per cent).

6 : 8-Diethyl-7-methyl-5-hydroxycoumarin, prepared similarly to 5-methyl-6-ethyl-7-hydroxycoumarin, crystallised from dilute alcohol in shining needles, m.p. $183-85^{\circ}$, yield 0.5 g. (Found* : C, 72.2; H, 6.8. $C_{14}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 72.4; H, 6.9 per cent). It did not show fluorescence in concentrated sulphuric acid or in alkali solution.

6 : 8-Diethyl-4 : 7-dimethyl-5-hydroxycoumarin, prepared by the method described for 4 : 5-dimethyl-6-ethyl-7-hydroxycoumarin, crystallised from dilute alcohol in brown needles, m. p. $179-80^{\circ}$, yield 0.5 g. (Found* : C, 72.9; H, 7.0. $C_{15}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 73.2; H, 7.3 per cent). It did not show fluorescence in sulphuric acid or alkaline solutions.

3 : 5-Diethyl-4-methyl-2 : 6-dihydroxybenzaldehyde (VIII) was prepared as usual from 4 : 6-diethyl-5-methylresorcinol (VII, 3 g.) dissolved in dry ether (110 c.c.) and zinc cyanide (4.2 g.). The dry hydrogen chloride gas was passed for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours. The crystalline ketimide hydrochloride was heated with water (200 c.c.) at 100° for 1 hour. The product crystallised from light petroleum ether (b.p. $69-95^{\circ}$) in flat shining yellow needles, m.p. $117-18^{\circ}$, yield 2 g. (Found*: C, 69.4; H, 7.9. $C_{12}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 69.2; H, 7.7 per cent). The *p-nitrophenylhydrazone* crystallised from hot acetic acid in deep red shining needles, m.p. $224-25^{\circ}$. (Found : N, 12.3. $C_{18}H_{21}O_4N_3$ requires N, 12.3 per cent).

Ethyl 6 : 8-diethyl-7-methyl-5-hydroxycoumarin-3-carboxylate from the aldehyde (VIII, 0.7 g.), malonic ester (0.54 g.) and piperidine (3 drops) crystallised from dilute alcohol in yellow wooly needles, m.p. $181-83^{\circ}$, yield 0.51 g. (Found : C, 67.1; H, 6.7. $C_{17}H_{20}O_5$ requires C, 67.1; H, 6.7 per cent). It showed no fluorescence in concentrated sulphuric acid or in alkali solution.

6 : 8-Diethyl-7-methyl-5-hydroxy-5' : 6'-dimethoxy-2 : 3 (3' : 2') indenobenzopyrylium Chloride.—Dry hydrogen chloride was passed for 2 hours into a mixture of the aldehyde (VIII, 0·8 g.) and 5 : 6-dimethoxy-1-hydrindone (0·71 g.) in dry ethyl acetate (5 c.c.). It was obtained in dark red needles which melted at 153°-54°. (Found : Cl, 8·8. $C_{23}H_{23}O_4Cl$ requires Cl, 8·9 per cent). The perchlorate melted at 240°-241°. (Found : Cl, 7·9. $C_{23}H_{25}O_8Cl$ requires Cl, 7·6 per cent).

4 : 6-Diethyl-2 : 5-dimethyl resorcinol (IX).—A mixture of zinc amalgam (from 10 g. of zinc dust), 20 c.c. of dilute (1 : 1) hydrochloric acid and the aldehyde (VIII, 2 g.) dissolved in ethyl alcohol was gradually heated at 100° until the yellow colour of the mixture was discharged (30 minutes). Longer heating is undesirable. The hot solution, after filtration, deposited on cooling a white spongy mass which crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 107°-108°. (Found : C, 74·6 ; H, 9·3. $C_{19}H_{19}O_2$ requires C, 74·2 ; H, 9·3 per cent). It gave a blue colouration with aqueous ferric chloride which disappeared after some time. It deteriorates rapidly on cooling, becoming deep brown even in a day and after two or three days becomes pasty. The di-p-nitrobenzoyl derivative crystallised from boiling acetic acid in tiny white needles, m.p. 257-59°, yield 1·7 g. (Found : N, 5·8. $C_{23}H_{21}O_8N_2$ requires N, 5·7 per cent).

The authors are thankful to Dr. T. S. Wheeler, Principal, Royal Institute of Science, Bombay, and to Dr. M. B. Rehinan, Principal, Ismail College, Andheri, for their kind interest during the progress of the work. The authors' thanks are also due to Dr. R. B. Forster, Head of the Department of Chemical Technology, the University of Bombay, for allowing some of the analyses to be carried out in his laboratory.

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Received January 6, 1936.

The analysis marked** is a micro-analysis, carried out by Dr. J. N. Ray of Lahore ; those marked * are micro-analyses carried out by Dr. Fischer of Germany and the remaining were done by one of the authors (P. R. M.).